

Fostering Autonomous Learning Through Padlet Integration in EFL Writing at a Vietnamese Public High School

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ABSTRACT

Autonomous learning has been regarded as an important learning method for students' achieving success in language learning, particularly in times of Vietnamese educational reforms and the new English language curriculum, where students are centered and able to improve their self-learning ability. While research mainly focuses on teacher beliefs in learner autonomy, there's a lack of studies on EFL student's perceptions and practices of autonomous learning in Vietnamese school settings. This study investigated the utilizing of Padlet to foster autonomous learning in EFL writing lessons among forty-four 10th graders at a public high school in the Mekong Delta, Viet Nam. The quantitative data were collected with the use of questionnaires and qualitative insights from the teacher's observations. Findings indicated that students held positive perceptions and demonstrated active participation in writing tasks through Padlet, suggesting its capacity to enhance self-directed learning. However, the study also acknowledged several challenges, including technical barriers, technical guidance shortage from teachers and time limitation. To resolve the obstacle and promote autonomous learning, the study recommended providing technical support to teachers and students, ensuring reliable and stable Internet access, and engaging students in writing tasks with clear expectations and criteria. Ultimately, it is important to incorporate digital tools, leverage students' writing skills, and continuously reflect on teaching practices for better fostering autonomous learning among EFL school students in Vietnam.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization, ability to use English effectively is undeniably a priority for students seeking to grasp global knowledge and international opportunities. With Vietnam's growing integration into the world economy, English proficiency – particularly in writing – has emerged as an important skill for those who seek access to scholarships, career opportunities, and academic resources worldwide (Nguyen & Doan, 2021). In this context, promoting autonomy in English learning is vital, as it empowers students to take control of their learning, overcome resource limitations and develop independent learning habits (Nguyen, 2009). Against that backdrop, Vietnam has issued national guidelines for implementing information technology (IT) and fostering learner autonomy in all levels of education (MOET, 20?? Xem lai bai Phan et al; MOET, 2024). Policies emphasizes enhancing digital transformation, strengthening online and hybrid learning, developing IT infrastructure, and expanding cashless payments. This aligns with the goal of

cultivating autonomous and digitally competent learners in Vietnam's reformed English curriculum.

Despite growing research on technological integration and learner autonomy in Vietnam, most studies have emphasized on higher education contexts, leaving secondary school settings relatively underexplored (Tran, 2019). Moreover, while studies on students' autonomy through using Padlet in EFL writing have been carried out in Vietnam, little research investigates the role of Padlet in fostering autonomous learning in school settings (Tran, 2019). Addressing this gap, this present study explores how Padlet can be used to enhance autonomous learning in EFL writing lessons among 10th graders at a public high school in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam. Specifically, it examines students' baseline autonomy levels, their perceptions and practices of self-directed learning through Padlet, and the influence of this tool on their engagement, motivation, and writing performance. Drawing on these findings, the study offers pedagogical recommendations for integrating Padlet to promote learner

autonomy within the Vietnamese high school context. Specifically, it investigates students’ baseline level of autonomous learning before implementing Padlet, their current habits, strengths, and areas for improvement in self-directing learning. It also explores the significance of Padlet in assisting learner autonomy by investigating how Padlet is employed to support EFL students’ self-directed learning as well as how it influences students’ learning outcomes, engagement, motivation, and language proficiency with a particular concentration on their ability to carry out independent learning process. Drawing on these findings, the study provides some recommendations for implementing Padlet in to promote learner autonomy in Vietnamese high school contexts.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Learner autonomy in language learning

Autonomy originates from the Greek words, *autos* (self, oneself) and *nomos* (law, rule, principle). Hence, the word can be explicitly understood as self-rule or self-government. Holec (1981, page number?) defines autonomy as “the ability to take charge of one’s learning”. Thereby, autonomous learners are known to have the ability to meet their own needs of learning contents and speed. As Benson (2013) noted, autonomy is the capacity to control one’s own learning. Learner autonomy is placed among academic innovations that “the need for individual’s freedom development is insisted by strengthening those abilities to let him act more responsibly in operating the society where he lives” (Holec, 1981, p.3). According to Allwright (1988), autonomy is a term referred to a radical restructuring of the whole conception of language pedagogy, involving the refusal of conventional academic setting structure and the presentation of wholly novel learning and teaching methods. A broader conception of autonomy is tentatively suggested by Wenden (1991), in which she attempts to put the learner training methodology in a broader theoretical framework of learner autonomy.

Promoting enduring learning is one of the fundamental goals of education, which helps equip the students with skills, knowledge, and beliefs in order to address all academic issues and teach them how to maintain enthusiasm about learning. As a result, fostering learner autonomy should be considered a leading goal that both educators and students attempt to achieve. Learners’ autonomy forms the basis for lifelong learning (Sigal et al., 2024) and laying the foundation of students’ autonomy in learning ensures that they keep their study going as far as possible. Hence, it is the duty of every teacher to improve students’ ability to learn autonomously and train “autonomous learners” to meet the increasing demand for economic and social development (Salokangas, 2017).

Learner autonomy benefits learners and teachers, helping increase the learning outcomes. Learner autonomy enhances EFL students’ proficiency and enables learners to control their learning (Rizki et al., 2023). Also, learner autonomy is picked

up through learners’ duties for their learning. There are reasons why autonomy is important in students’ learning process. Firstly, autonomy is one of the fundamental human needs (Ryan et al., 1995). Secondly, autonomy gives birth to motivated and creative learners. When the students engage in their own learning, they can address motivational issues effectively and overcome temporary lapses in motivation. Finally, communicative competences in second or foreign language learning classes can be enhanced with learner autonomy. Learners with a higher level of autonomy can have greater chances to improve their communicative abilities compared to those who lack it.

Autonomous learners, according to many leading researchers in the field of autonomy such as Holec (1981), Benson (2013), Borg & Al-Busaidi (2012), Wenden (1991), Little (2004), and Dickinson (1995), have some key characteristics which can be categorized into three interconnected themes: Metacognitive abilities (the capacity for self-regulation, which involves strategic planning and goal setting, self-monitoring and strategic adjustment, and evaluation and critical reflection), Affective traits (including intrinsic motivation and persistence, responsibility for learning, and self-awareness and a positive self-concept) and Managerial skills (the practical execution of learning control, translating intention into concrete action, involving resource management and time and space organization).

2.2. Technology in EFL education

Technological development provides learners the opportunities to expand the space where they learn beyond the four walls of the classroom and shift from the traditional education to a more meaningful process. According to Pourhossein Gilakjani (2017), technology has changed the teaching process of the English language appreciably. Moreover, the implementation of digital technology to the instructional setting activities increases learners’ enthusiasm and motivation towards learning a language and gaining knowledge. Additionally, Costley (2014) pointed out that integration of technology assists learners to be more engaged in the lesson and become information seekers, problem solvers, collaborators and communicators. Lastly, technology offers a learner-centered classroom setting where learners eagerly join the classroom tasks and become autonomous learners.

Padlet is a versatile platform where users can create one or numerous walls to post videos, images, documents, and audio. According to Holovina (2021), Padlet is defined as a “digital notice board”, an “online bulletin board”, an “online post it board”, a “virtual wall”, a “dashboard”, etc. It is a free web-based application with walls, on which learners post words, links, pictures, files, and even videos for language learning. Anyone possessing the link or address to a specific wall can see these contents on the wall through mobile phones (with Android or iOS system). Padlet users could develop suitable contents in the walls and use them in the class.

Padlet is regarded as a valuable assistant for English language

instruction in several ways. First, Padlet can be used to supplement learners' brainstorming and generate ideas (Zhi & Su, 2015) through activities like brainstorming, discussion and project work. Second, teachers and students can collect resources and materials easily through Padlet (Holovina, 2021). Third, Padlet facilitates discussions and peer feedback (Sari, 2019). Finally, the best way to present information visually is through Padlet walls. Different studies show numerous advantages of Padlet in English Instruction such as its 'ability to boosts on-the-spot collaboration since any student can see the work someone else is uploading; its storage ability, and its convenience for different learning styles.

However, there are still some major obstacles to Padlet users, including poor infrastructure like the shortage of essential digital equipment and resources and the Internet connection; instructors' negative attitudes towards digital technology, digital illiteracy, lack of technical support, and time insufficiency.

2.3. Related studies on learner autonomy

2.3.1. Overseas studies

Research on the role of teachers in enhancing learner autonomy shows the classification of three categories: teacher as manager and organizer; teacher as facilitator; and teacher as counsellor (Breen & Mann, 1997). Sarason (1999) described a model of five affordances in enhancing learner autonomy, which are engagement, exploration, personalization, reflection, and support. In another study, Melvina and Julia (2021) suggested that learner autonomy had a very close relationship with technical, psychological, and sociocultural, and language proficiency.

On the other hand, only few researchers did more investigations on the learning environment, but in other aspects like at university level or with the integration of many other technological tools. Hamilton (2013) wrote about ways to promote autonomy in foreign language learning in a digital learning space. Roh and Kim (2019) studied the ways to foster learner autonomy in a technology-integrated language class in a university in Korea.

Meanwhile, there are many studies on the utilization of Padlet to foster students' writing skills. Dollah et al. (2021) suggested ways that motivate EFL learners to write with the utilization of Padlet Application. Zahroh et al. (2023) investigated Padlet's effectiveness in 11th graders' writing skill in a school in Karya Pembaharuan.

2.3.2. Studies in Viet Nam

Le (2013) studied the ways to foster learner autonomy in language learning in tertiary education in Viet Nam. Besides, Van Loi (2016) made some observations about English language teachers' beliefs and practices regarding learner autonomy in Asian contexts. Bui (2018) discussed the development of learner autonomy in Vietnam's universities and colleges, which has been beset with matters of conceptualization and operation at the administrative and academic levels. Tuan and Anh (2023) published his articles

about Vietnamese EFL students' perceptions and practices about learning autonomy in English language learning.

Research on E-learning and learner autonomy in an EFL class in tertiary institutions in Viet Nam is conducted by Lien (2022), in which she emphasized the significance of learner autonomy in online courses and the need to promote it. However, few studies on the use of Padlet to promote students' autonomy have been carried out up to now. Nguyen and Trang (2023) researched the implication of peer feedback on Padlet to enhance EFL students' email writing and motivation.

Although a significant amount of literature has been published on learner autonomy in higher education, how to develop learner autonomy among high school EFL learners in Vietnam is undetermined and more importantly the use of tasks for cultivating their autonomy in the Mekong Delta, where traditional teacher-centered practices are dominant. However, there is still a lack of any empirical research on the use of digital platforms for pedagogical purposes to promote self-directed learning in this context. Hence, in order to bridge the gap, there is much to be gained from investigating how Padlet can foster autonomy in a high-school EFL classroom in the Mekong Delta while providing both theoretical considerations and practical ideas for EFL teaching.

2.4. Research objectives and research questions

The objective of this research is to explore role of Padlet in fostering learner autonomy among EFL students at a public high school in the Mekong Delta. Specifically it seeks to investigate students' perceptions of using Padlet in English learning, examine how students practice autonomous learning behaviors through Padlet activities and identify the facilitating factors and challenges influencing the use of Padlet for fostering learner autonomy.

The research aims to answer the two following questions: The first question is “What are EFL students' perceptions of using Padlet in their English learning?” and the second question is “How do students practice autonomous learning when engaging with Padlet?” and the last question is “What do the facilitating factors and challenges influence the use of Padlet to support learner autonomy?”

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research design

This research employed action research design to investigate and enhance the efficacy of using of Padlet to promote learner autonomy among EFL learners at a public high school in the Mekong Delta. In addition, this study also applied a mixed methods of collecting and analyzing data to achieve deep and broad understanding and help avoid the existing limitations of using solely quantitative or qualitative approaches independently so that quantitative results can also be validated or interpreted with qualitative data as well.

3.2. Participants

The study employed a purposive sampling technique to select

the participants who could provide rich and relevant data aligned with the research objectives. The total number of the participants is forty-four, including twenty-three males and twenty-one females, all of whom are from class 10A3 at Chau Van Liem High School, An Giang Province. These students had just started their first year of high school, providing a baseline for implementing the intervention. The class demonstrated a valuable diversity in English proficiency levels, based on their entrance exam results: 5 students were below average, 12 average, 14 good, and 13 excellent. This variation was critical for the action research design as it allowed for observations on how Padlet-based tasks influenced students across the proficiency spectrum.

3.2. Data collection instruments

The study employed an action research method, in which two primary data collection instruments were implemented, the questionnaire and the systematic observation. The questionnaire, administered twice (pre- and post-intervention) was significant for gathering standardized, quantitative data on students’ perceptions, attitudes and reported practices regarding Padlet’s impact on autonomy, self-regulation and motivation. Comprising 13 items on a five-point Likert scale, it also includes some open-ended questions for qualitative feedback on experiences, challenges, and facilitating factors. The observations on the process of students’ task completion on Padlet were made and recorded

simultaneously with the process of students’ doing on Padlet. Key indicators of learner autonomy such as on-task behavior (active posting outside class, self-correction, and constructive feedback) and off-task behavior (passivity, irrelevant comments) were carefully monitored. Moreover, there are also a checklist that specifically tracked time management, self-direction, collaboration, self-assessment, and creativity. To ensure the rigor of the study, reliability and validity procedures were undertaken before the data collection. The questionnaire, developed from an existing questionnaire for autonomy and technology integration, was validated by two senior lecturers of EFL to ensure that each item is relevant. Comprehensibility and appropriateness of items were also ensured by administering similar questions to 44 students as a pilot administration. The Cronbach’s Alpha for the internal consistency reliability was 0.838, which is considered highly reliable for educational research instruments. Additionally, the observation checklist was also validated by an expert review and aligned to the theory in a structured way.

3.3. Data collection procedure

The study lasted 11 weeks and was divided into two main cycles of action research, allowing for refinement of the Padlet integration strategy after the first set of observations and reflections. Each cycle included the stages of planning, action, observation, and reflection (Kemmis & McTaggart, 1988).

Table 3. Action Research Cycles, Activities, Instruments, and Purposes

Week	Activity	AR phase	Instruments	Purpose of the phase
1	Orientation Section & Pre-Questionnaire	Plan (Cycle 1)	Questionnaire, Training	Establish baseline perceptions and familiarize students with Padlet and research expectations (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015)
2-5	Lessons (Topics 5,6)	Act & Observe (Cycle 1)	Observation checklist	Implement the initial Padlet strategy and collect real-time data on student engagement and initial autonomy levels (Dörnyei, 2007)
6	Reflection section & strategy adjustment	Reflect (Cycle 1) & Plan (cycle 2)	Observation data analysis	Analyse data from Weeks 2-5, identify challenges (e.g., low feedback quality, time management issues), and refine the Padlet task instructions for Cycle 2 (Kemmis & McTaggart, 1988).
7-10	Lessons (Topic 7,8)	Act & Observe (Cycle 2)	Observation Checklist, Final Observations	Implement the revised Padlet strategy. Special attention is given to changes in collaborative behavior and engagement compared to Cycle 1 (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).
11	Post-Questionnaire & Final Reflection	Reflect (End)	Post-Questionnaire	Measure overall change in perceptions and reflect on the final effectiveness of the Action Research process (Cohen et al., 2018).

Note. AR = Action Research.

Cycle 1: Identification, Action, and Initial Reflection
The first cycle lasted for 5 weeks, from week 1 to 5. Planning

phase address the initial problem of low student autonomy, particularly in independent writing, involving developing and

uploading Padlet-based tasks for two thematic units and an orientation session taken place on the first week. In this session, students were trained on Padlet features, ethical considerations were introduced and pre-study questionnaire was distributed to establish baseline attitudes towards autonomous learning. Then, the action phase (from week 2 to week 5) observed students ‘assignment completion and engagement in peer-feedback session. Simultaneously, the observation phase was carried out systematically by the researcher, using a structured checklist and field notes to record students’ engagement levels, interaction patterns, and self-correction frequency. The cycle ended with the reflection stage at the end of week 5, which revealed a mixed response: while some students demonstrated high engagement and self-regulation, others struggled with providing constructive feedback and maintaining engagement.

Cycle 2: Adaptation, Intensive Action, and Final Evaluation
The second cycle also commenced with Planning in week 6. This planning directly applied the insights gained from the first reflection to adapt activities for two remaining thematic units with a view to promoting more balanced participation and achieving a higher level of independent engagement. Next, the action phase from week 7 to 10 experienced students’ applying the adapted recommendations, posting, commenting, and redrafting their assignments according to their friends’ comments and feedback. The observation phase during this phase maintained similar systematic approach but intensified its focus on revised autonomy indicators: self-direction, creativity, time management, and the quality of collaboration. Week 11 saw the final reflection with the distribution of post-questionnaire to measure the final

changes in students’ attitudes and perceived effectiveness of Padlet. The data in the reflection demonstrated significant gains in overall engagement, cooperative work, and student autonomy. Despite these improvements, the reflection also acknowledged minor persistent matters, including technical glitches and inconsistent contributions from a minimal number of students, which would be addressed in the study’s overall conclusions and implications.

3.4. Data analysis procedure

The responses collected from the questionnaire were compiled and analyzed quantitatively using descriptive statistics (Creswell, 2014). First, the quantitative data were transformed into coded categories. They were then entered into SPSS and analyzed statistically for frequency, mean scores, and standard deviations. The field observations of the participants’ doing assignments were initially noted down and then analyzed using a qualitative thematic analysis approach. In this study, observation notes were first transcribed and then categorized into themes and patterns regarding students’ interaction, participation, and autonomy while they were doing their assignments on Padlet walls.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Students’ perceptions of autonomous learning via Padlet

A paired samples t-test from the questionnaire results was conducted to make a comparison between students’ average scores before and after the intervention.

As shown in table 4.1, the mean score before using Padlet was M=3.39, SD=0.41, while the mean score after the implementation increased to M=3.77, SD=0.44.

Table 4.1. Mean comparison of students’ autonomous learning

Measure	Mean	SD	N
Pre-intervention	3.39	0.41	44
Post-intervention	3.77	0.44	44

The paired samples t-test indicated that students’ autonomous levels before using Padlet are significantly different from those after using Padlet. Additionally, the mean score showed a sharp increase after the integration by M=0.38 and SD=0.03.

Moreover, the result also shows a number of $t(43) = -4.315$, $p = .000$ (meaning $p < 0.001$), which suggests that the

integration of Padlet had a beneficial effect on enhancing students’ autonomous learning.

Besides, the post- questionnaire results also revealed students’ positive attitudes towards Padlet’s features. 86% found Padlet easy to use and suitable for their learning styles. 80% reported increased motivation and independence when using Padlet. Most students agreed that Padlet supported goal setting, collaboration, and feedback.

4.2. Students’ practice on Padlet (observation- based evidence)

Based on the four observed writing topics, students exhibited strong autonomous learning behaviors.

Table 4.2. Summary of observational findings

Criteria	Summary
Time Management	44/44 students met deadlines in all four tasks
Self-Direction	100% of students posted without teacher reminders
Collaboration	Over 1,015 comments and feedback exchanged via Padlet

Self-Assessment	Students revised their posts at least twice based on feedback
Creativity	Creative layouts appeared in 5–8 posts per topic
Challenges	Technical issues decreased from 3 (Topic 5) to 0 (Topic 8)

During the observation phase, students’ autonomous behaviors were examined through their participation in four writing topics posted on Padlet. Key aspects of autonomy—including time management, self-direction, collaboration, self-assessment, and creativity—were closely monitored.

Time management: All forty-four participants were reported to consistently complete their assignments on time across the writing tasks in the four topics assigned by the teacher. This constancy clearly supports the perspective that the participants were able to plan their learning schedule effectively and maintain punctuality consistently throughout the process.

Self-direction. 100% of the participants readily carried out their assignments on Padlet walls without the need for reminders from the teacher. In comparison to traditional classroom practices where students often require teacher prompting, this behavior signifies a notable shift toward autonomous learning when technology is effectively integrated.

Collaboration: Peer interactions increased steadily in numbers from 240 to 261 and then to 271 comments and feedback entries, indicating heightened involvement and peer support. Students’ feedback became more academic and constructive over time. They began to focus not only on surface-level issues but also on deeper aspects such as writing structure, word choice, and logical coherence. For instance, Minh Le commented, "Line 2: You should replace the word ‘method’ instead of ‘way of learning’ to avoid repetition," which targeted lexical repetition. Similarly, Quynh suggested, "I think you should separate the supporting sentence and the explanation into two different sentences," reflecting awareness of paragraph development. Each post received between 4 to 6 comments, predominantly from peers and occasionally from the teacher. The number of comments indicate the frequency of peer feedback, together with the improvement of quality of each feedback, suggests that Padlet really served as an effective medium to enhance collaborative learning and peer endorsement.

Self-assessment: 95% of the participants revised their work at least twice, demonstrating an ongoing process of reflection and progress. This iterative process suggests that the participants viewed feedback more as a chance for learning and developing than as a final judgment for corrections.

Creativity: 59% of all writing posts were creatively presented, including colorful and patterned backgrounds, various fonts, inspiring images, and the inclusion of engaging statistics or graphics. Such creative choices could reflect both the participants’ digital literacy and their personal investment and ownership of their learning process.

4.3. Facilitating factors, challenges and solutions associated with the implementation of Padlet

4.3.1. Facilitating factors

Accessibility and ease of use. Data gathered from the questionnaire uncovered that 95% of the participants reported Padlet was easy to handle. Besides, this user-friendly interface encourage them to post, edit, and revise their posts independently without their teacher’s continuous guidance. Moreover, observation data further confirmed this; 100% of students posted their writing on time and without any reminder, which indicates that Padlet can empower students to take initiative and manage their writing tasks effectively.

Flexible time management. Approximately 82% of students agreed that Padlet enables them to have the accessibility to review and track their progress anytime and another 89% agreed or strongly agreed that Padlet offers them the flexibility to work at their own pace. In addition, more than 90% reported that Padlet allowed them to manage their time allocation flexibly. This result was revealed in the observation records, which showed that 100 percent of students completed assignments within deadlines.

Peer collaboration and interaction. 91% of students enjoyed the collaborative features of Padlet that allowed them to interact with peers and teachers, such as commenting on and giving feedback on their peers’ posts. This collaborative feature was also evident in the observational data, where the number of peer comments steadily increased from 240 to 271 across topics 5 to 7.

Self-assessment and revision practices. Nearly all students (98%) in the questionnaire acknowledged that Padlet enabled them to access, review and track their learning progress. This was strongly supported by observation: at least 95% revised their writing twice or more based on peer and teacher feedback.

Motivation and creativity. From the questionnaire, students expressed that features such as colorful backgrounds and multimedia options made learning more enjoyable and engaging. Moreover, the real-time updates and feedback from teachers and peers and the sense of accomplishment when completing tasks or contributing to a shared board make Padlet a wonderful motivation in their learning. Besides, the observations confirmed this, as approximately 59% of student posts were presented with creative designs—using varied fonts, vivid images, and engaging statistics or graphics.

4.3.2. Challenges

11% reported facing technical difficulties when using the platform; another 14% found it hard to use Padlet without teacher guidance; 9% experienced limited internet access. Additionally, 5% reported the limited time allocated for Padlet activities within lessons.

The “Challenges” in the observation framework were students not knowing how to use Padlet, being distracted, and encountering connection errors. Some students initially faced difficulty in logging in with their own account (Observation note 1-3). Across the observed topics, specific technical challenges were noted. Students were unable to log in with their correct accounts. Besides, distraction when using digital platforms was reported in open-ended responses. The final challenge was the limited technical skills.

4.3.3. Students' suggested solutions

From open-ended questionnaire responses, there were numerous recommendations from the participants. First of all, students proposed more teacher guidance in the first week and an ongoing technical support during the research process. Secondly, better Wi-Fi support during writing tasks is necessary. Thirdly, the use of Padlet in other subjects to maximize its utility should be encouraged.

The evidence collection from both the questionnaire and the observation indicates that Padlet significantly contributed to students' development of autonomous learning skills. Both quantitative scores and qualitative behaviors confirmed its effectiveness. The findings also pointed practical factors and challenges relevant for future implementations.

4.4. Discussions

4.4.1. Padlet as a tool for autonomous learning

The figure collection of this study signifies that Padlet can work as a beneficial digital assistant in fostering autonomous learning among EFL learners.

The questionnaire statistics reveal that most students had conclusive perceptions of Padlet. They agreed on its convenience, accessibility, collaboration nature, creativity, motivation, flexibility, and self-assessment and actively engaged in learning activities through the platform. The results well match many previous research which highlights Padlet's capacity to enhance learner autonomy with countless opportunities for collaboration, interaction, and self-directed learning (Suhardiana, 2023). Moreover, such outcomes are also consistent with the usefulness of Padlet pointed out by Dollah et al. (2021). This aligns with Padlet promoting student ownership of learning in tertiary settings (Roh & Kim, 2019), which benefits also applicable to younger learners in a high school context according to the present study.

The observation data corroborated these findings, demonstrating students' ability to manage their time effectively, complete assignments independently, and be creative in doing tasks. Additionally, the students consistently met deadlines without reminders, backed up their peers' work with constructive feedback and autonomously revised their writing posts with the help of their peers' feedback and comments. Such behaviors are consistent with the research on peer feedback on Padlet to enhance EFL students' writing and motivation (Nguyen & Trang, 2023).

4.4.2. Padlet for engagement and collaboration

Padlet significantly enhances learner engagement and collaboration in learning activities. That 84% of participants

acknowledged Padlet as a valuable platform for collaborative projects suggests that Padlet's features support group work effectively, allowing students to pool their knowledge freely, split tasks easily, and construct understanding collectively among members. Padlet holds a power of learners' participation encouragement. The high percentage of agreement (98%) confirmed Padlet's roles in encouraging active participation and peer feedback. Padlet is also reported to effectively foster teamwork. The function of organization can assist participants to structure their collaborative tasks, making it easier for them to coordinate their own work and efforts towards a common goal.

4.4.3. Challenges in using Padlet to foster autonomous learning among EFL learners

One of the greatest challenges is the technical barriers. Some students reported that they were unable to log in the account or the Internet connection was sometimes cut off. Additionally, others expressed a need for more technical guidance from their teacher and additional time to complete their assignments.

4.4.4. Solutions to overcome challenges

The first set of solutions is given to technical barriers. It firstly involves providing comprehensive initial and ongoing technical support and training- such as guided training sessions or video tutorials- to get students familiar with the platform (Amin & Sundari, 2020). In addition, it is essential to ensure reliable and stable Internet access and intensify lesson time, especially in under-resourced settings (Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2015). Finally, scaffolding activities can also ease the transition to digital tools, encourage participation, and gradually increase student independence (Van de Pol et al., 2010).

Another set of solutions is reserved for enhancing learner motivation and autonomy such as designing engaging tasks with clear expectations and criteria (Martin & Bolliger, 2018); making diverse and vivid lessons by incorporating diverse topics connecting with students' interests and real-life contexts (Deci & Ryan, 2000); and having positive attitudes towards students' work and efforts.

5. CONCLUSION

The study has offered compelling evidence and valuable insights into the effectiveness of Padlet to foster EFL learners' autonomous learning and enhance student engagement and collaboration. It, however, presents certain unavoidable limitations that may affect the comprehension and generalizability of the findings. These can be listed as the small-scale number of participants, the limitation of the generalizability of the findings, the absence of triangulation from multiple data sources which declines the findings' validity and reliability.

Here are some important guides for teachers to take into consideration when applying Padlet in the classrooms. Firstly, guidance and training should be sufficient. Teachers ought to instruct students how to set realistic goals, track progress,

handle learning time well, and reflect on their learning. Secondly, feedback practices and a safe and supportive environment should be available for peer interaction. Teachers ought to inspire learners to give as much feedback as possible. Thirdly, teachers need to carefully consider students’ emotional engagement on the lessons. Teachers should strive to incorporate a wide range of activities to stimulate mutual contact, collaboration, and a communal meaning within the classroom. Finally, there should be continuing consideration and modification of teaching practice. Teachers need to constantly assess the effectiveness of their technological integration strategies and make adjustments based on student progress and observed outcomes.

Several avenues for further research could be expanded upon these findings. First, future research need to set up studies with a significantly wide-ranging sample of EFL learners to deal with the limitation of sample size. Next, future research should look into the effectiveness of Padlet in a variety of educational settings beyond a single high school context so as to conquer the setting-specific feature of the study. Then, future research ought to incorporate a mix-method approach with a greater emphasis on qualitative data and objective measures to alleviate the reliance of self-reported questionnaire data and observation notes.

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